

THE ESSENCE OF DIVERGENT THINKING IN FOREIGN AND NATIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL LITERATURE

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Abstract: in this article, on the basis of world experience, a scientific analysis of the research on divergent thinking in the modern education system is carried out.

Key words: divergent, intellectual, concept, identification, attention, perception, association process, thinking, association, motive, activity, convergence, reproductive, creative thinking, independent, heuristic.

The concept of "divergent thinking" was introduced to science for the first time by J. Gilford (1967). He showed the main difference between two mental operations: convergence and divergence.

Divergent thinking is defined by him as "a type of thinking in a different direction". This kind of thinking allows for different ways of solving a problem, leading to unexpected conclusions and results. J. Gilford considered the operation of divergence, along with the operations of transformation and implication, to be the basis of creativity as a general creative ability. Divergent thinking relies on imagination. It assumes that there can be more than one answer to a question, which is a condition for the creation of unique ideas and self-expression of a person.

According to J. Gilford, divergent thinking is characterized by four main qualities: speed, flexibility, originality, accuracy.

Speed is the ability to express the maximum number of ideas in a certain time. Moreover, in this case, not their quality, but their quantity is important.

Flexibility is the ability to express different ideas.

Originality is the ability to create new non-standard ideas. It can also be manifested in answers that do not correspond to generally accepted answers.

Clarity is completeness, the ability to perfect or complete one's thoughts.

Later, other attempts were made to define divergent thinking, but they brought little innovation to its concept proposed by J. Gilford. In general, divergent thinking is independent, exploratory, unique, effective thinking, characterized by inversion and discreteness.

Convergent thinking, unlike divergent thinking, is characterized by the accuracy and speed of finding the only possible (normative) answer in accordance with the requirements of a given situation.

In foreign psychology, the concept of "divergence" has been discussed for a long time, but in domestic psychology, until recently, this problem existed only among mathematicians and natural scientists. But the Russian psychologist L. Dorfman described divergent thinking and noted: "Metaphorically, divergent thoughts can be likened to an encyclopedia: it contains many articles, each on a separate topic, the articles are related to each other. are not directly related and they form together. strong intellectual resource and potential". The promotion of discrete, parallel, alternative, complementary (or mutually exclusive) ideas characterizes divergent thinking, which produces not only ideas, but also differentiated and weakly interconnected ones. . "That's why they're different," explains Dorfman. Each of the divergent ideas is a relatively independent (autonomous) idea; it can be personal and separate from other ideas. Divergent ideas in the aggregate are a cognitive "marketplace" of ideas with their own variety, variety and choice. These are the various possibilities that create uncertainty and volatility.

The term "divergence" (lat. *cue[^]rege*) means the discovery of divergences. This phenomenon is universal and describes the process of infinite complexity of all forms of living and inanimate existence of self-organizing matter. The principle of divergence is important for understanding the processes of self-organization in general and the evolution of the living world in particular.

For example, in biology, Darwin used the concept of divergence to describe the differentiation of their characteristics during the evolution of organisms. The phenomenon of divergence describes the evolutionary development of dissimilar characters in closely related species originating from one organic ancestor (prototype). This explains the diversity of cultivated plant varieties, domestic animal breeds and biological species in nature.

One of the mechanisms of divergence is bifurcation. According to N.P. Moiseev, any developmental processes, including social processes, can be characterized by Darwin's trinity; variation, heredity and selection. Bifurcation is one of the main selection mechanisms along with adaptation. Moiseev derives from the existence of boundary conditions in the organization of the system, the passage through which leads to a sharp change in the quality of the processes in it, to a change in its organization. The transition from the old organization of the system to the new is uncertain, because many new forms of organization may appear. The uncertainty of the future is the main characteristic of bifurcation. The future state of the system when the characteristics of the system exceed the threshold value is determined by many random factors. The determined

uncertainty, randomness, uncertainty of the future indicates the absence of a thinking mechanism that determines its direction and is conditioned by previous analysis.

It is necessary to pay attention to several important aspects characterizing divergence: 1) divergence as discreteness of signs (characteristics); 2) inconsistency as a decrease in connection and an increase in the differentiation of signs (characteristics); 3) inconsistency as the coexistence and operation of characteristics (characteristics) in a parallel, alternative, complementary (or mutually exclusive) mode; 4) inconsistency leading to increased uncertainty and diversity.

In a number of works (I. Ya. Lerner, D. Campbell, A. Naysner) it is shown that divergent thinking is actualized in the initial stages of problem solving, and convergent thinking is actualized in the later stages. In this case, divergence is replaced by actualization of distant zones of semantic space.

S. Mednik sees the process of divergent thinking as follows: there is a problem, and the intellectual search starts from its content in different directions - in the semantic space. Divergent thinking - lateral peripheral thinking, "close to the problem" thinking. According to S. Mednik, the more remote the elements of the problem are, the more creative the solution process will be. So, the essence of creativity is not in the specific features of mental operation, but in the ability to overcome stereotypes at the final stage of mental synthesis.

In psychology, the direction of research that reveals the physiological mechanisms of the development of thinking has gradually developed and continues to develop. In a number of works (Y.A. Ponomareva, D.N. Zavalishina, A.V. Brushlinsky) it was shown that the problem of the psychology of thinking - the problem of mental "mechanisms" should be solved in the process of studying nervous mechanisms. reflection process.

Correct orientation to the perception of a problematic situation is apparently carried out according to the principle of feedback. This means that there is a regulatory interaction of two broad streams of information (nerve impulses). When the search and motor phases of the reaction coincide, the beginning of the fourth stage - recognition can be recognized. In this case, the answer (solution) becomes a signal for the end of the reaction. The psychological description of the reaction in a problematic situation reflects two main psychological connections - perception and understanding of the meaning of the

phrase - instructions, on the other hand - recognition that corresponds to the expected image of the object.

In a problematic situation, a divergent type question causes an impulse from one pole (component). This impulse turns out to be the cause of the imbalance of the internal system. The second pole must respond to this effect to bring the system back into equilibrium. The nature of the reverse action (response) is determined, on the one hand, by the nature of the internal process, and on the other hand, it is determined by the nature of the other component. Thus, the nature of the reverse movement is determined by the specific internal structure of the component.

When talking about divergent thinking, the interest in right brain problems cannot be ignored. In the neurophysiological and neuropsychological literature, the theory of functional asymmetry of the brain (N. Genzels, S. Kalagan, S. Taylor, L. Thurston, L. Volas, S. Kogan) is widespread. so far, the left hemisphere is responsible for rational-logical processes, and the right hemisphere is responsible for intuitive processes. In our opinion, the results of medical and neurological studies should be approached with caution, as facts that are not sufficiently supported by research results are used. There is a general consensus (Torrance) that the left hemisphere processes information sequentially and linearly, analytically and logically. True, on the contrary, global, relative, synchronous and intuitive, that is, not linear. The perception of structures, connections, the sense of beauty are the functions of the right hemisphere, which implements holistic perception. The processes of the right hemisphere can be surprisingly subtle, ambiguous: the outcome is unpredictable. But the inspiration and intuition that accompanies a particular activity of the right hemisphere creates an entirely new result that arises from the rich integration of convergent thinking.

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